

INFLUENCE OF THE SHEARING OF TEXTILES ON THE IN-PLANE PERMEABILITY

M. Arnold^{1*}, M. Cojutti², P. Mitschang¹

¹ Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Kaiserslautern, Germany

² Audi AG, Ingolstadt, Germany

* Corresponding author (matthias.arnold@ivw.uni-kl.de)

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1 General Introduction

Liquid composite molding is an important process for the manufacturing of automobile, aeronautic, engineering, and wind energy components. The increasing complexity of the components leads to higher shear angles during draping. In these highly sheared areas of the component the fiber volume fraction increases. Due to the higher fiber volume content the risk of dry spots during the injection is high because of lower permeability. To predict the highly draped areas in a component at a very early stage of product development a draping simulation can be performed. The draping simulation gives information about the shear angles in every area of the component. This information can be used for a filling simulation of the component if the permeability of the reinforced textile is known for different shear angles and different fiber volume fractions.

Smith et al. investigated the effect of shear deformation on the permeability for non-crimp fabrics and woven fabrics at a very low fiber volume fraction between 0.3 and 0.45. The cavity heights were constant, thus the fiber volume fraction increased due to shearing and the permeability decreased [1]. Heardman et al. investigated the in-plane permeability for sheared glass weaves and a sheared carbon weave. It was determined that the increasing fiber volume content and the reorientation of the fibers have an influence on the permeability [2]. Louis et al. and Endruweit et al. investigated the influence of shearing on the permeability of glass and carbon woven fabrics. The cavity heights for the measurements in the initial state (not sheared) and in the sheared state were kept constant. The influence of the increasing fiber volume content and the reorientation of the fibers had an influence on the

permeability and on the orientation angle of the flow ellipse [3, 4]. Demaria et al. investigated the influence of the shearing of a carbon woven fabric at a constant fiber volume fraction on the in-plane permeability [5, 6].

In this paper the influence of the shearing on the in-plane permeability of glass fiber woven fabrics and carbon fiber non-crimp fabrics are compared. Therefore, the textiles are measured at three different fiber volume fractions in the initial state (not sheared) and in the sheared state. Based on this data it is possible to predict the permeability data for a desired fiber volume fraction in the not sheared and sheared case. Thus, it is possible to readout the sheared permeability value at the increasing fiber volume content due to shearing [7].

2 Experimental setup

2.1 Material

Two different glass fiber fabrics from the company Hexcel were investigated. The first is a plain weave with an areal weight of 286 g/m², the other is a twill weave with an areal weight of 385 g/m², see Tab. 1. Furthermore, two non-crimp carbon fabrics $\pm 45^\circ$ from the company Sigmatec were investigated. The NCFs only differ in the yarn count of the stitching yarn, see Tab. 2.

2.2 Method

In the case of 0°/90° non crimped fabrics (NCFs) the material is laid up on a flat table and clamped into two shear bars along the 0°-direction. One bar is fixed and the other one (opposite side) is moved for a certain distance, corresponding to the desired shear angle (see Fig. 1). For $\pm 45^\circ$ NCFs the textile is pulled in 90°-direction until the calculated

rectangular square is reached. For each shear angle the final square size can be calculated by trigonometrically relations based on the initial square size. Due to the elongation in 90°-direction the textile shortens in 0°-direction and a certain shear angle appears (see Fig. 2).

After the shearing the shear angle can be controlled with help of angle measurements along the reinforcing yarns. This ensures that the correct shear angle is adjusted and that a homogeneous shearing over the complete textile is achieved.

After the desired shear angle is adjusted over the whole layer, several textile layers are laid on a CNC cutter (Bullmer Spezialmaschinen GmbH L5001LV) in the same manner. Then specimens for the permeability measurements are cut out of the stack. After cutting the single measurement specimens the shear angle is verified again by angle measurements along the reinforcing yarns.

The in-plane permeability is measured with IVW's permeability measurement cell 2D-Capa-Perm, see Fig. 3 [8-10]. For the measurements rapeseed oil is injected into the preform and the radial flow front is detected by eight linear capacitive sensors. To ensure 2D-flow (no flow in through the thickness), a hole (12 mm) is punched through the middle of the 465 mm by 465 mm sized preform. The desired fiber volume fraction is adjusted with the help of different cavity height frames and the number of layers of the material. For all tests the material is positioned in the same orientation. A constant injection pressure is used to inject the rapeseed oil into the preform. The viscosity of the oil is very well known by temperature. The permeability is calculated with the help of Darcy's law.

Each material is measured in an unsheared state and at different shear angles. The permeability of the unsheared and sheared material is measured at three different fiber volume fractions. Every measurement at one certain fiber volume fraction and shear angle is done three times. For each shear angle and material the in-plane permeability K1 and K2 is plotted in a diagram versus the fiber volume fraction. Moreover, the orientation angle α of the permeability K1 and the anisotropy K2/K1 is calculated for every permeability measurement (Fig. 4).

3 Results

The permeability values for all materials are plotted versus the fiber volume content as shown in Fig. 5 for the glass fiber fabric Hexcel 1103. Every adjusted shear angle is measured at three different fiber volume contents. The permeability decreases exponentially with respect to the fiber volume fraction for every adjusted shear angle. Due to the logarithmic scale on the y-axis the exponential fitting function is a straight line in the diagram. Because of shearing the fiber volume content (fvc) increases at a constant cavity height, see equation (1).

$$fvc_{sheared} = fvc_{not\ sheared} / \cos(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

Herby α is the shear angle, see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The influence of the increasing fiber volume content due to shearing at a constant cavity height is significant. Besides the fiber volume content the reorientation of the fibers has a significant influence on the permeability and on the orientation angle of the main flow direction K1, resp. on the orientation of the flow ellipse. For the woven glass fiber fabrics and the carbon NCFs the effect of the increasing fiber volume fraction due to shearing and the effect of the reorientation of the fibers has an influence on the permeability.

3.1 Influence of shearing on the in-plane permeability of glass fiber fabrics

In Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 the permeability measurements for the glass fiber fabrics are shown. The permeability is measured at three fiber volume contents for the not sheared case and for three sheared cases (10°, 20°, and 28°).

The influence of the changing fiber content due to shearing at a constant cavity height is very high. In Fig. 7 the K2 Permeability values of Fig. 5 are extracted and enlarged to show the influence of the increasing fiber volume fraction due to shearing at a constant cavity height. An initial fiber volume fraction of 50 % (not sheared) was chosen and the sheared fiber volume content was calculated by equation (1). With the fiber volume fraction at each shear angle the permeability value can be readout. For the fabric Hexcel 1103 the K2 permeability from not sheared (50 % fvc) to 28°-sheared (56.6 % fvc) decreases by 80 %. In this manner the permeability value of a sheared textile can be readout of such a diagram (like Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) for a desired initial

fiber volume fraction in the not sheared case. Of course this is only possible in the measured shearing range. In strong curved components shear angles up to 50° are reached which decreases the permeability in these areas even more.

Besides the influence caused by the increasing fiber volume fraction due to shearing, the new fiber orientation also plays an important role. Fig. 8 shows how the shear angle influences the orientation angle of the permeability. With increasing shear angle the permeability orientation angle β increases, too. The major flow direction K1 changes due to shearing. For the woven glass fiber fabrics the orientation angle changes almost like equation (2) for the fiber volume content range from 45% to 55%, see Fig. 8.

$$\beta = \alpha/2 \quad (2)$$

The anisotropy of the permeability is calculated by equation (3).

$$\text{Anisotropy} = K2/K1 \quad (3)$$

In Fig. 9 the anisotropy of the permeability for the fabric Hexcel 1103 is shown for all measured shear angles over the fiber volume content. In the not sheared state the anisotropy of the fabric is between 0.55 and 0.63, depending on the fiber volume content. Although the linear density and the yarn density in warp and weft direction are equal for the fabric Hexcel 1103 the anisotropy value in the not sheared case is quite low. The anisotropic permeability in the not sheared state can be explained by the crimp in warp and weft direction (Tab. 1). The undulation of the weft yarn is much higher than that of the warp yarn. This occurs because of different yarn tensions in warp and weft direction during the textile manufacturing process. The higher crimp in weft direction seems to decrease the permeability in weft direction compared to the warp direction.

With increasing shear angle the anisotropy value decreases, see Fig. 9. The lowest anisotropy of 0.28 is reached for the highest shear angle (28°) at a fiber volume content of 53%. The anisotropy value of the fabric Hexcel 1103 is decreasing with increasing fiber volume content in all shear states.

Fig. 10 shows the anisotropy of the permeability for the fabric Hexcel 1113. The linear density is not balanced for the fabric Hexcel 1113; the warp yarn

is denser (340 tex) than the weft yarn (272 tex) while the yarn density is nearly equal. That explains why the anisotropic value in the not sheared permeability measurement is very low (0.2 to 0.25). Due to shearing the anisotropy does not change significantly. The shearing of the Hexcel 1113 does not influence the anisotropy value strongly, which is for all measurements between 0.15 and 0.4. The lower anisotropy of the fabric Hexcel 1113 is also obvious in Fig. 6 because of the higher distance between K1 and K2 compared to the fabric Hexcel 1103 (Fig. 5).

3.2 Influence of shearing on the in-plane permeability of $\pm 45^\circ$ non-crimp fabrics

Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show the permeability measurements of the NCFs Sigmatec DMC 2711270 and 3011270. The permeability is measured at three different fiber volume fractions for the not sheared state and for the three sheared states (10°, 20°, and 30°). The difference between the K1 and K2 permeability is very small which means that the material has a high anisotropy value and therefore a low anisotropy.

Fig. 13 shows the orientation angle of the permeability with respect to the shear angle. For this diagram the orientation angles of the nine permeability measurements (three measurements at three fiber volume contents for one shear angle) were averaged. The orientation angle is defined like in Fig. 4. The 0°-direction (production direction) is defined along the stitching yarn which does not change due to shearing. For the not sheared case the orientation angle for both materials is oriented in 0°-direction along the stitching yarn. Due to shearing the orientation angle changes dramatically. At 20° shear angle the orientation angle switched to 80° which means the major flow direction for higher shear angles is approx. perpendicular to the unsheread flow direction. The orientation angle at 10° shear angle does not play an important role, because at this shear angle the anisotropy value of the permeability is very high (>0.72), which means the ratio of the half-axes of the flow ellipse is about 0.85 (square root of 0.72). The flow ellipse is nearly circular, thus the orientation angle does not have a high relevance.

The anisotropy of the permeability for the NCFs Sigmatec DMC 2711270 and 3011270 is shown in

Fig. 14. With help of this diagram the switching of the orientation angle can also be explained. In the not sheared case the permeability is oriented in 0°-direction. Due to shearing the anisotropy increases until a certain shear angle is reached. After that the anisotropy decreases. That means the permeability in 90°-direction increases in relation to the permeability in 0°-direction. Thus, the anisotropy increases until the permeability in 90°-direction is higher than in 0°-direction. At that point the K1 permeability switches to the 90°-direction. After the K1 permeability is oriented in 90°-direction the anisotropy decreases.

3.3 Variability in the permeability measurement

The permeability measurement of reinforcing textiles strongly depends on the homogeneity of the measured textile. Endruweit et al. summarize this in [11] in the chapter „understanding variability in the permeability of non-crimp fabrics composites reinforcements“. This shows that there are always variations due to material inhomogeneity in textiles. With the permeability measurement cell 2D-capperm the flow front is tracked along eight sensors. These eight sensors are positioned diametral in the lower mold (see Fig. 3). That means there are four pairs of opposing sensors that can be compared. If the flow ellipse is perfectly point symmetrical the ratio of the diametral sensors is one. Thus, the ratio or the deviation of the diametral sensors is an indicator for the homogeneity of the material [9]. If the deviation between the diametral sensors is high the material has a more inhomogeneous flow behavior than a material where the deviation of diametral sensors is low. In the measurements it was detected that the deviations of the diametral sensors increase with increasing shear angles. This effect was more obvious for the NCFs. That can be explained by the shearing defects which occur more often for NCFs compared to woven fabrics.

4 Discussion

Woven glass fiber fabrics

Fig. 5 shows that the permeability value K1 increases in the sheared state at the same fiber volume fraction. On the other hand the permeability value K2 decreases if the woven fabric is sheared. This was also determined by Heardman et al. [2] and by Endruweit et al. [4]. For the fabric Hexcel 1113

this effect cannot be seen. A reason why the behavior of the fabrics differs can be found in the anisotropic flow behavior in the not sheared state. Due to the anisotropic textile structure (see Tab. 1) the permeability of the fabric Hexcel 1113 is already very anisotropic for the not sheared case. The shearing of the fabric Hexcel 1113 does not lead to a more anisotropic behavior in the fabric as described above.

Fig. 8 shows the orientation angle β (see Fig. 4) of the permeability with respect to the shear angle. The orientation angle is nearly constant over the fiber volume content. For example the orientation angle of the not sheared fabric Hexcel 1103 is approx. 0° for 45 %, 50 %, and 55 % fiber volume content. This clarifies that the orientation angle is not dependent on the fiber volume fraction, although there are some small deviations due to variability in the permeability measurement. Thus, the change of the fiber volume fraction is not responsible for the change of the orientation angle of the permeability. The new fiber orientation that occurs due to shearing seems to change the orientation of the permeability. For the glass fiber fabrics the orientation angle changes by the equation (2).

It was found that the anisotropy value of the fabric Hexcel 1103 (which had an anisotropy value of approx. 0.6 in a not sheared state) decreases for an increasing shear angle. This relationship was confirmed through further permeability measurements of the fabric Hexcel 1265 (plain weave). For this material which is not presented in this study the initial anisotropy was approx. 0.7. The anisotropy value decreased with the increasing shear angle to an anisotropy value of 0.4 at a shear angle of 29°. Besides that several measurements were found in the literature where the anisotropy value decreases due to an increasing shear angle.

For the Hexcel 1113 the anisotropy does not change significantly with increasing shear angles. A reason for this behavior is probably the low anisotropy at the not sheared state (0.2 to 0.25). Another woven fabric Hexcel 1035 (twill 2/2 weave) with a very low initial anisotropy value (0.16 to 0.28) was investigated at the IVW. The fabric does not change anisotropy due to shearing. The anisotropy value after shearing was in the range from 0.16 to 0.3 for all shear angles investigated.

It seems that a decrease of the anisotropy value due to increasing shearing only occurs for woven fabrics with an initial anisotropic value above 0.5.

± 45° non-crimp fabrics

The in-plane permeability values for NCFs show a significantly lower permeability compared to the woven glass fiber fabrics investigated in this study.

The change of the fiber volume content due to shearing at constant cavity heights also has a huge influence on the permeability of the NCFs. For the NCFs the influence of the change of the fiber volume content due to shearing can be considered like in Fig. 7 for the glass fiber fabrics.

The reorientation of the reinforcing fibers has a significant influence on the orientation angle of the permeability (Fig. 13). The orientation angle in the initial state is approx. aligned in the 0°-direction. From at least 20° shear angle the orientation angle switches to the 90°-direction. The reinforcing fibers in the not sheared case are oriented in ± 45° for the two balanced NCFs investigated in this study. That means for a central injection (if the fibers are perfectly oriented and balanced) that a circular flow occurs. The stitching yarn is oriented in 0°-direction and seems to enhance the flow in this direction. That could explain why the orientation angle is aligned in the 0°-direction in the not sheared case. Due to shearing the angle between the reinforcing yarns gets smaller, which means that the orientation of the bigger amount of the reinforcing yarns is oriented in the 90°-direction (see Fig. 2). The stitching yarn orientation is not changed due to shearing. Due to the reorientation of the reinforcing yarns the flow in 90°-directions is fostered. If this theory is right there must be a certain shear angle where the influence of the stitching yarn (fosters flow in 0°-direction) and the influence of the reorientation of the reinforcing yarns (fosters flow in 90°-direction) are equal. At this certain shear angle a circular flow must occur for a central injection. This certain shear angle must be between 0° and 20°. Due to inhomogeneity in the textile and the variations of the adjusted shear angle the shear angle where the two effects are equal depends on the above mentioned parameters.

The anisotropy with respect to the shear angle for the two NCFs is plotted in Fig. 14 and confirms the theory described above. The anisotropy in the not sheared case is between 0.65 and 0.7 and the orientation angle is aligned in 0°-direction. With

increasing shear the anisotropy value increases to a maximum and after that the anisotropy value decreases (see Fig. 14). Probably there is an anisotropy maximum value of 1 for a shear angle between 0° and 20° where the effect of the stitching yarn and the effect of the shearing of the reinforcing yarn are balanced.

5 Conclusion

In this paper the influence of shearing on the in-plane permeability of two glass fiber fabrics and two carbon NCFs ± 45° was investigated. For both materials the influence of the increasing fiber volume content due to shearing at a constant cavity height is significant. The K2 permeability of the material Hexcel 1103 decreases by 80 %. Besides the influence of the increasing fiber volume content the reorientation of the fibers has a major influence on the permeability. The influence of the reorientation of the fibers is very different for both materials.

The orientation angle of the glass fiber fabrics increases due to the shearing of the textile by half of the shear angle. For a shear angle of 10° the orientation angle is 5° and so on. The anisotropy for the glass fiber fabrics Hexcel 1103 decreases due to shearing. For the Hexcel 1113 (a very anisotropic textile) the anisotropy does not change significantly due to shearing. Two further investigated glass fiber fabrics (not presented in this study) showed the same behavior. It seems that the anisotropy of fabrics with an initial anisotropy value >0.5 are influenced by shearing whereas fabrics with a very low anisotropy value are not influenced by shearing.

The investigated NCFs have a very different behavior compared to the glass fiber fabrics. Due to shearing the orientation angle switches abrupt from 0°-direction to the 90°-direction of the textile. This switching of the orientation angle occurs at a certain shear angle between 0° and 20°.

Summarizing, the shearing has a huge influence on the permeability which has to be taken into account for process simulation. The permeability of different materials can have a very different behavior due to shearing.

6 Acknowledgement

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Fig. 1. Shearing of a 0°/90° reinforced fabric

Fig. 2. Shearing of a $\pm 45^\circ$ reinforced non-crimp fabric, not sheared (left) sheared (right)

Fig. 3. Permeability measurement cell 2D-Capa-Perm

Fig. 4. 2D-permeability measurement method to determine the permeability of textile reinforcement

Fig. 5. Permeability measurement data versus the fiber volume content for the fabric Hexcel 1103 at different shear angles

Fig. 6. Permeability measurement data versus the fiber volume content for the fabric Hexcel 1113 at different shear angles

Fig. 8. Orientation angle of the permeability with respect to the shear angle at different fiber volume contents for the glass fiber fabric Hexcel 1103

Fig. 7. Influence of the increasing fiber volume content due to shearing at a constant cavity height on the permeability (shown for the K2 permeability of the woven fabric Hexcel 1103)

Fig. 9. Influence of the shear angle on the anisotropy of the permeability values for the woven fabric Hexcel 1103

Fig. 10. Influence of the shear angle on the anisotropy of the permeability values for the woven fabric Hexcel 1113

Fig. 12. Permeability measurement data versus the fiber volume content for the NCF Sigmatex DMC 3011270 at different shear angles

Fig. 11. Permeability measurement data versus the fiber volume content for the NCF Sigmatex DMC 2711270 at different shear angles

Fig. 13. Orientation angle of the permeability with respect to the shear angle of the NCF Sigmatex DMC 2711270 and 3011270

Fig. 14. Influence of the shear angle on the Anisotropy of the permeability values for the NCFs Sigmatex 2711270 and 301 2170

Tab. 1. Textile specifications for glass fiber fabric Hexcel 1103 and Hexcel 1113

Manufacturer designation	Hexcel 1103	Hexcel 1113
Weave	Plain	Twill
Fiber type	(EC9 68) x 3	(EC9 68) x 3
Yarn density in warp / weft [picks/cm]	7/7	5.9 / 6.6
Linear density in warp / weft [tex]	204 / 204	340 / 272
Areal weight [g/m ²]	286	385
Crimp warp / weft [%]	0.57 / 1.47	0.43 / 0.94

Tab. 2. Textile specifications for the NCF Sigmatex DMC 2711270 and Sigmatex DMC 3011270

Fabric	Manufacturer designation	Sigmatex DMC 2711270	Sigmatex DMC 3011270
	Fiber orientation	±45°	±45°
	Areal weight [g/m ²]	302	304
	Fiber typ and finish	T700SC 60E	T700SC 60E
Stitching yarn	Material	Black Polyester	Polyester
	yarn count [dtex]	36	80
	Gauge [1/inch]	E5	E5
	Weight [g/m ²]	4	6
	Stitching type [mm]	Hybrid	Hybrid
	Stitching length [mm]	2.86	2.86

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